

Charming Tales of Kingfisher: Vietnamese Culture and Life Lessons.

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Wild Wise Weird*”

Rosa Marie, Rodrigo

United States, January 11th and 16th, 2025.* * *

Rosa Marie: Very Endearing!

This collection of short stories, originally written in Vietnamese, is charming and engaging. The accompanying illustrations are stunning. It's been a long time since I've read a book of short stories, but I truly enjoyed this read. It teaches a lot about Vietnamese culture, which is fascinating. A great read! [1]

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Screenshot. Review of “*Wild Wise Weird*” by Rosa Marie [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 16th, 2025.

Rodrigo: This book made me smile

This is book is a delight. The collection of short stories of humor, satire, and wisdom made me smile. I loved the perspective of Kingfisher, who teaches important life lessons while navigating the bird world. The stories are light but also thought-provoking, with themes of community, leadership, and personal growth. The tone of the writing kept me entertained most of the time. Some stories felt a bit slower pace, but overall this is a very nice and enjoyable read [2].

Rodrigo

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Verified Purchase

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Screenshot. Review of “*Wild Wise Weird*” by Rodrigo [2]. Reviewed in the United States on January 11th, 2025.

(*) Note: This paper reprints Rosa Marie, Rodrigo's reviews [1, 2] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [3]. The reprint's title is created based on the review's content.

References

[1] Rosa Marie (2025, Jan. 06). Very Endearing!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RPN8ZAP09FEJU>

[2] Rodrigo (2025, Jan. 09). This book made me smile.
<https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R3N9CME2ID2UIZ>

[3] Vuong, Q. H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6/>